

Rodent borne zoonoses: An Overview

Bhavin P Katira

¹Ph.D. Scholar, Division of Veterinary Public Health and Epidemiology, ICAR-Indian Veterinary Research Institute, Izatnagar, Bareilly, U.P., 243122

Introduction

The word "zoonosis" (plural: zoonoses) was first used in 1880 by German pathologist Rudolf Virchow, who discovered a connection between human illnesses and animal diseases. The World Health Organization (WHO) later defined zoonoses as those diseases and infections which are naturally transmitted between vertebrate animals and man. There are around 1415 infectious organism species that can cause disease in people. 868 (61%) of them are zoonotic in origin, and 175 pathogenic species are connected to illnesses that are causing emerging infectious diseases. Seventy-five percent of these emerging pathogens are zoonotic.

Rodents are mammals of the order Rodentia which are extremely diverse in their ecology and they are most abundantly found in almost every terrestrial habitat. There are over 2000 species of rodents across the globe which are distributed in every continent except Antarctica, But the most hotspot locations with high diversity of rodent species are Southeast Asia, Southeast China, tropical areas of Africa and South America, and Western and Eastern Europe. Rodentia contribute about 43% of the total number of mammalian species of the world. While in India, rodents are the second highest mammalian species followed by chiropterans by contributing 24%. Out of these 43% rodent species, 217 species are reservoirs harbouring 66 zoonoses caused by viruses, bacteria, helminths and protozoa and play a major role in their transmission and spread in different ways.

Transmission

Rodent-borne zoonoses can be transmitted through two different pathways; directly or indirectly. In the direct transmission, diseases are transmitted by biting, e.g., rat bite fever or by inhaling the germ containing faeces of rodents, e.g., hantavirus infection or, because humans consume food products or water that is contaminated with rodent faeces, e.g., salmonellosis or humans can come in contact with

surface water that is contaminated with rodent urine, e.g., leptospirosis. While indirect transmission can be seen by mean of ectoparasitic arthropod vectors (ticks, mites, fleas), e.g., plague, murine typhus. Another way of indirect transmission is the ingestion of meat. Rodents that are accidentally or on purpose ingested by livestock can transfer pathogens which can result in human morbidity if these food products are not-thoroughly cooked and consumed, e.g., toxoplasmosis.

Table 1: The important rodent borne diseases prevalent in India are as follows

Disease	Agent	Rodents as Carrier/Reservoir
Leptospirosis	<i>L. icterohemorrhagiae</i>	Carrier
Salmonellosis	<i>S. enteritidis</i>	Carrier
Tularemia	<i>Francisella tularensis</i>	Carrier
Listeriosis	<i>L. monocytogens</i>	Carrier
Plague	<i>Yersinia pestis</i>	Reservoir
Lyme disease	<i>Borrelia burgdorferi</i>	Reservoir
Scrub typhus	<i>Orientia tsutsugamushi</i>	Reservoir
Murine typhus	<i>Rickettsia typhi</i>	Reservoir
Rickettsial pox	<i>Rickettsia akari</i>	Reservoir
Q fever	<i>Coxiella burnetii</i>	Reservoir
Rat bite fever	<i>Streptobacillus moniliformis</i>	Reservoir
Hantavirus	<i>Hantavirus, Bunyaviridae family</i>	Carrier
Crimean-Congo haemorrhagic fever	<i>CCHF, Bunyaviridae family</i>	Reservoir
Kyasanur Forest Disease	<i>KFDV, Flaviviridae</i>	Reservoir
Tick borne encephalitis	<i>TBEV, Flaviviridae</i>	Reservoir
Lassa Fever	<i>LASV, Arenaviridae</i>	Carrier
Lymphocytic Choriomeningitis (LCMV)	<i>LCMV, Arenaviridae</i>	Reservoir
Venezuelan haemorrhagic fever	<i>Guanarito virus, Arenaviridae</i>	Carrier
Hepatitis E	<i>HEV, Calciviridae</i>	Reservoir
Toxoplasmosis	<i>Toxoplasma gondii</i>	Reservoir
Babesiosis	<i>B. microti</i>	Reservoir
Cryptosporidiosis	<i>Cryptosporidium</i>	Reservoir
Chagas disease	<i>Trypanosoma cruzi</i>	Reservoir
Leishmaniasis	<i>Leishmania donovani</i>	Reservoir
Giardiasis	<i>Giardia lamblia</i>	Reservoir
Human fasciolosis	<i>Fasciola hepatica, F. gigantica</i>	Reservoir
Taeniasis	<i>Taenia solium</i> in pork <i>Taenia saginata</i> in beef	Reservoir

Plague

Plague is a rodent-borne bacterial zoonotic disease caused by *Yersinia pestis*, a member of the *Enterobacteriaceae* family. It is gram-negative bacillus. It can occasionally spread to humans, has complex zoonotic/epizootic cycles, and can result in rare instances, outbreaks, or even significant epidemics. The clinical manifestation of bubonic plague is the most typical in humans. Bubonic forms can progress to septicemic illness, and one to three percent of them can become secondary pneumonic plague, which can spread from person to person by respiratory droplets. Untreated patients might have a mortality rate of up to 100% between 1 and 4 days after the beginning of symptoms. The bacteria are enzootic in rodents. The most common hosts are *Rattus rattus* (domestic black rat) and *Rattus norvegicus* (brown sewer rat) and *Xenopsylla cheopis* (oriental rat flea) is the most common and efficient vector. Between 2013 and 2018, WHO documented 2,886 cases and 504 fatalities (with a reported case fatality of 17.5%). China, Mongolia, the Russian Federation, Kyrgyzstan, Peru, Bolivia, Uganda, Tanzania, and the US all frequently report sporadic occurrences of the human plague. Over 200 mammals, including rodents and lagomorphs, have been documented to be infected, and over 30 distinct flea vectors, including possible reservoir hosts, have been suspected of being involved in transmission in various regions of the world.

Leptospirosis

The involvement of rodents in the epidemiology and transmission of *Leptospira* is well documented on a global scale. The most significant carriers of many pathogenic serovars of *Leptospira* spp., which may infect people and other animals, are wild rats (*Rattus* spp.), particularly the Norway/brown rat (*Rattus norvegicus*) and the black rat (*R. rattus*). According to the World Health Organization (WHO), leptospirosis is a serious emerging and re-emerging disease that affects both humans and animals. Over 1 million individuals are thought to have been infected, and the illness results in 60,000 fatalities year. Leptospirosis is most prevalent in tropical areas, including Asia-Pacific, Latin America, and the Caribbean, with an estimated >10 occurrences per 100,000 people each year.

Scrub typhus

Scrub typhus is an emerging rodent-borne zoonotic disease. It is caused by *Orientia* spp. and transmitted by larvae of trombiculid mites, called chiggers. This pathogen is transmitted by bites of infected trombiculid mites ('chiggers') which are hosted by various rodent species, such as the Norway rat (*R. norvegicus*), the lesser bandicoot (*Bandicoota bengalensis*), the bandicoot rat (*Bandicoota indica*), house mouse (*Mus musculus*), the striped-field mouse (*Apodemus agrarius*), and the Japanese grass vole *Microtus montebelli*. Scrub typhus is endemic to a part of the world known as the

“tsutsugamushi triangle”, which extends from northern Japan and far-eastern Russia in the north, to northern Australia in the south and to Pakistan in the west. Increase in the prevalence of scrub typhus has been reported from some Asian countries, which coincides with the widespread use of beta-lactam antimicrobial drugs and urbanization in rural areas. There was a total of 64 studies from South India, 46 studies from North India, 13 from North-East India, 13 from the East, and four from the West reporting 55.5%, 31.5%, 7.4%, 4.5%, and 1.1% of scrub typhus cases, respectively.

Kyasanur Forest Disease

Kyasanur Forest Disease (KFD) is a re-emerging zoonotic disease caused flavivirus which is found in forest rodents in south western India. Disease is associated with sudden onset of high-grade fever, prostration, nausea, vomiting, diarrhoea and occasionally neurological & haemorrhagic manifestations. Infected ticks are the source of infection to human. KFD was initially reported in black-faced langur (*Semnopithecus entellus*) and red-faced bonnet monkeys (*Macaca radiata*) in Kyasanur forest of Shimoga district in India. About 400-500 humans were also affected with the disease who had visited the affected forest at that time. The tick species *Haemaphysalis spinginera* is widely distributed in the deciduous and evergreen forests of India and Sri Lanka. KFD was reported to be endemic in Sagar, Sorab, and Shikarpur taluks of district Shimoga. Many sporadic cases of KFDV have been also observed every year in the endemic state of Karnataka mostly in Shimoga, Chikmagalur, Udupi, Uttar Kannada, and Dakshina Kannada district since 1957, after the discovery. During the year 2004-2012, many outbreaks occur in four districts of Karnataka state with 556 reported human cases. KFD outbreak was also reported in the Bandipur Tiger Reserve in Chamaraajanagar among the forest workers during 2012 to 2013. During the same period, in Nilgiri and Wayanad the virus was detected in ticks and/or monkeys. During 2014-2015, in new regions of Wayanad and Malappuram districts of Kerala, KFD outbreaks were explicitly observed and more recently, it has been reported in Goa, India.

Crimean Congo Haemorrhagic Fever (CCHF)

Crimean-Congo hemorrhagic fever (CCHF) is a tick-borne viral disease caused by the CCHF virus (CCHFV), an RNA negative single-stranded virus of the genus *Nairovirus* in the *Nairoviridae* family. The virus has been identified in Africa, Asia and Europe in territories located south of the 50th North parallel, the area inhabited by the main vector, ticks of the genus *Hyalomma* spp. CCHFV is implicated in outbreaks with a very high mortality rate (10-40%). CCHF has been isolated from rodents thus, play an important role in the tick cycle. CCHF is endemic in Africa, Balkans, Middle East and Asia with estimated cases of 10,000 to 15,000 each year. In India CCHF has been reported from Gujarat since 2011 to 2019. CCHF outbreak was also recorded from three districts Jodhpur, Jaisalmer, and Sirohi of

Rajasthan state since August 2019 till November 2019.

Rodent control strategies

The rodent population can be controlled by regulating the births, deaths, immigration or and emigration the population size may be regulated which occur at rates that depend on population density. The immigration can be prevented and reduced by using barrier methods, rodent proofing premises, electric fences, diversion feeding, ultrasound and electromagnetic devices and chemical repellents. Pest birth rate can be reduced effectively by implemented by removal of nesting opportunities - clean farming practices and sanitation measures, the odors and ultrasonic devices has a potential of disruption of reproductive behavior in house mice. The alpha chlorohydrin, a male antifertility compound also has good result. The pest death rate can be enhanced by trapping and hunting and using the predators viz feral cat, barn owls, Indian mongoose.

The acute rodenticides zinc phosphide, aluminum phosphide, barium carbonate, arsenic trioxide, strychnine alkaloid, thallium sulphate, alpha-naphthyl thiourea (ANTU), norbormide, scilliroside (red squill); sodium fluoroacetate, vacor (RH-787) and a gophacide have very good results. Similarly, rodenticides with subacute action, are bromethalin, flupropradine, calciferol (ergocalciferol, vitamin D2) and cholecalciferol (vitamin D3). The first-generation anticoagulants include warfarin, fumarin, coumatetralyl, diphacinone and chlorophacinone. And second-generation anticoagulant rodenticides are difenacoum, brodifacoum, bromadiolone, flocoumafen and difethialone.

Conclusion

Besides economic losses through spoilage of feed or structural damage, rodent presence on livestock farms can have serious consequences for public and animal health. Rodents play a significant role in transmission of a large number of diseases to humans. The risk levels vary between the different pathogens, a better surveillance of rodent populations is important in order to predict future disease prevalence. Huge species diversity among mammalian order and their ecosystem roles makes rodent control difficult. Recent reports of resurgence of rodent borne diseases warrants need of strengthening surveillance to track disease before it spills to human population.

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